

The Effect Of The Utilitarian Connotation On Criminalizing Homosexuality

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Abstract

The subject of the study raises legal problems, the most important of which is the difference in the position of the penal legislation regarding the treatment of abnormal sexual practices. Islamic Sharia has approved the principle of the absolute prohibition of these practices, and it sees them as the embodiment of all the meanings of perversions of common sense and righteous morals, and a blatant attack on the law of God. While some legislations view homosexuality and the influence of Western philosophy, as a permissible act, and confirm that this practice, with its two parts (sodomy and lesbianism) is organized under the umbrella of the sexual rights of the individual that should not be violated, as long as it is based on the consent of its adult parties, while some legislations approached The other position is the approach of Islamic law, in terms of criminalizing this practice, and singling out texts and rulings of its own.

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Introduction

The abnormality of the reaction because it represents a deviation from the voice of human instinct and abnormal behavior, and these atrocities are repulsed by healthy skin, as confirmed by the heavenly laws prohibiting homosexuality because it involves many evils of them. An assault on morals as well. Such as assaulting the symptoms that result from this physical and psychological health act, and exposing the annihilation of the human race to disrupt the institution of marriage, which is one of the most important and harmful functions of reproduction, and leads you to the spread of crimes. Therefore, all the laws of Paradise and Islamic Sharia in particular are unanimous in prohibiting a deviant act with its well-known assumptions, and there is unanimity in this way; this is because it contradicts God's creation and good taste, and the lofty goal of the legality of marriage, which is to preserve dignity and offspring, and to prevent forbidden mixing. However, this phenomenon did not die, and it remained a secret. Different societies are aligned with their development and cultures, passed down from generation to generation. They have their supporters and followers from various segments of society. But the danger in that is that in the last two decades of the last century it has been openly practiced, and even boasted of belonging to the sect of its supporters and disciples, to the utmost testimony. What is worse is that its proposals and the opinions of its supporters have become the focus of the attention of the United Nations and the international community, which seeks to highlight them and give legal and moral legitimacy to their practices under justifications. Respecting sexual freedom and human rights, and facing the strange intellectual tide on the social fabric of Arab countries. So the study poses a big problem regarding the position of Western laws on homosexuality? Is this situation similar to some Arab laws? In order to clarify this issue is addressed as follows:

Second, the traditional concept of homosexuality

Homosexuality is any deviation from the normal course of abundant gratification of all kinds. Whoever engages in sex other than his normal position is considered a homosexual (1); It was defined as (a deviation from the legally defined path or forms of sexual practice in which the owners depart from the usual natural means of sexual intercourse, meaning that the homosexual person is the one who finds sexual pleasure away from the actual process of intercourse between the male and female through marriage) (2). It was said that it is (a pathological condition that represents a danger to the individual himself or to the members of the community in which he lives, and requires intervention to protect the individual and society from him) (3). And the jurist (Guebogw) defined homosexuality as ((all actions, practices or behaviors that contain excitement and attraction towards another person of the same sex)) (4).

In sum, homosexuality is a type of sexual needs that are satisfied through sexual practices that are outside the familiar of the formative nature and social custom, and thus it expresses a deviation in the normal sexual practice that exists between the organism and its counterpart of the same type, or with individuals. These practices with them, such as incest, children, the dead, animals, and the like; As a result, the homosexual person

is the one who finds sexual pleasure away from the natural process of intercourse between a male and a female. Through the foregoing, we can define homosexuality as every practice, regardless of its form, in which sexual enjoyment is achieved between two people of the same sex away from the usual way and the correct framework achieved for sexual intercourse stating the meaning of homosexuality.

Third: The religious concept of homosexuality

Islamic Sharia approved the principle of absolute prohibition of homosexuality, then described it as a crime in all cases, because it is harmful to health, moral corruption, deterioration of nature, the spread of vice, and the erasure of manhood. A felony of femininity that cuts the family apart. In other words, Islamic law has adopted the moral rule as the basis for criminalizing deviant sex. Because the matter is linked to the idea of the legal practice of sex, and the final result of Sharia criminalizing homosexuality in order to preserve morals, and it is one of the most important goals that Sharia sought. To achieve (5) Christian law has a strict position on the prohibition of same-sex relations and so on. The beings that men refuse to live with are other than women (6). As for mj, it is limited to the prohibition of homosexuality in Islamic law only, but it was forbidden in the laws of those of us who were from the Children of Israel in the Torah. Nor vetiver, for it was mentioned in the Torah (Do not grow with a woman, for it is an abomination) (7) as it was mentioned in the same book (If a man lied about a male and a female, then at that time) both committed an abomination because of it. They will kill with their own blood (8) Hence the Jewish religion is the practice of homosexual conduct between males and the terrible sin must be abstained. And the punishment is murder, chivalry and bravery, going to modesty and bravery, failing in the filth and corruption of masculinity, a crime against femininity, and degrading one's neighbor's sense of land to a low rank above which animals are exalted.

Fourth: The philosophical basis for permissibility of sodomy

The philosophy and scope of criminalizing homosexuality varies depending on the objectives of the punitive policy in each legislation. The honorable Islamic Sharia considers these practices the embodiment of all perverse meanings of logic and morals, and a flagrant violation of God's Sharia and its provisions in regulating sexual relations between the sexes in order to preserve lineage. Preventing their mixing, perpetuating offspring, fighting immorality and vices, and the accompanying incurable and contagious diseases, and as a result, they diagnose in them an imminent danger that threatens the moral structure of the individual and their livelihood. Family and then society as a whole. Other sexual practices, such as rape, adultery and the like, have regulated their provisions and tightened the criminal punishment imposed on them (9) While the philosophy of criminalization differs in positive legislation, as this legislation - and with the influence of Western philosophy, whether Latin or Anglo-Saxon - sees this practice in all its parts (sodomy and lesbianism) organized. Under the umbrella of individual sexual rights that may not be violated, as long as they are based on the consent of the adult parties, and from this perspective some legislation considers it a permissible act that does not require regulation or the intervention of the criminal legislator, while some other man-made legislation, due to the influence of this philosophy, is lenient In mentioning provisions about homosexuality, but when talking about moral or sexual crimes, pay attention to the essential degree of the crime. Coming in second place are rape and crimes beyond that, considering that rape is sexual intercourse without consent and, as a consequence, an assault on sexual freedom. (10) not in order to prevent lineage mixing, or to preserve the moral and ethical aspect of the individual and society as is the case in Islamic law, while some other man-made legislations followed the approach of Islamic law, in terms of criminalizing this practice and the uniqueness of its texts and provisions. These acts of sodomy are among the major sins that Islamic Sharia has rejected, and could not be tolerated, and he vowed to practice curses and punishment in this world and the hereafter. It protects the family from the causes of collapse, as it is the basic cell in building society, and the disintegration of the family threatens its security and public order (11) Returning to the utilitarian connotation of homosexuality, it is based on philosophical foundations that are completely different from the rules of morality based on the principle of perfection, and these foundations are linked to the values of personal utilitarianism and considerations based on ideas of liberation that call for getting rid of the restrictions of religion and the rule of moral rules, and making personal freedom the basis on which it is based. . Ethics in all areas, this led to the emergence of a new concept of sexual acts based on personal freedom and social benefit, meaning that all abnormal sexual acts are a personal right of the individual to dispose of them of his own free will. It is considered legal even if such behavior is considered contrary to the rules of religion or morals, because utilitarian philosophy believes that human happiness increases with personal pleasure and reduces pain, so homosexuality is an exchange between the benefit of adults, albeit in fact pathological. Selfishness. Desires (12)

One of the most important principles on which the utilitarian philosophy is based is the complete separation between religion and the state on the one hand, and morality and positive law on the other, so the prevailing principle in the philosophy of criminalization and punishment is that legislation from Western countries is based on the fact that the function of the penal law must be consistent with Human tendencies and the abolition of moral rules and religious values (13) that is, the penal code protects the interest that it considers worthy of criminal protection, a matter that the law is not subject to evaluation, away from these rules because it is not a subject of its interest. Rather, utilitarian thought views morals as individual and relative, so the criminal law

should not interfere in the private lives of individuals or criminalize sexual acts that affect morals, because it is not a guardian of the morals and conscience of the individual. (14) The idea of consensual sexual acts became the basis for the legality of sexual intercourse, so the protection of sexual freedom should be a task of criminal law. Legally regulating these acts and granting them criminal protection, which led to the emergence of a new type of sexual relations, including homosexuality (15) it is clear from the foregoing that the function of criminal law, according to the utilitarian philosophy, is not to protect morals and to spread virtue among people. Instead, the moral virtue must be left to their conscience, which the law stops at its limits and does not go beyond, that is, not to criminalize an act that violates morality; because the basis of criminalization stems from protecting one's sexual freedom and preventing harm to others. As for the moral meaning, it is based on the fact that the purity of the show is not the right of the owner except in his face. on others, but it is his duty to himself as well. The moral concept aims to protect the body from all kinds of illicit sex. European legislation until the eighteenth century ensured that every relationship outside of marriage was illegal and therefore punishable crime (16) Criminal laws currently apply two directions in criminalizing dishonorable acts.

The first trend

It goes to the legality of sexual practices that can only take place through marriage. The other practices are criminal in order to preserve public morals. Supporters of this tendency tend to protect honor per se, and thus honor killings have been extended to all normal sexual relations, so they are criminalized. It is a relationship between a man and an unmarried woman, whether this relationship takes place with or without her consent and whether they are adults or not. It also criminalizes unnatural sexual relations such as sodomy (the sexual relationship between men) and lesbianism (the sexual relationship that occurs between females), as well as intercourse between animals and incest. ... etc. (17)

The second trend

It recognizes the sexual freedom of individuals, which leads to the restriction of honor killings, since any sexual relationship that takes place with consent is considered a legitimate relationship, so the supporters of this trend do not require the existence of a legitimate relationship. Link. The relationship between the two parties to the sexual relationship, and thus this will lead to restrictions in the criminalization of sexual relations that occur at all without consent or the presence of consent, but were not significant (as a result of young age) (18)

Fifth: Examples of some legislation affected by utilitarian thought regarding homosexuality

Many countries of the world have begun to enact laws to decriminalize homosexuality, recognizing the right of homosexuals to enter into same-sex partnership or same-sex marriage with legal implications, to the point of prohibiting and criminalizing discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation. Through the provisions of the Penal Code. He parallels against homosexual families the natural family (19) with the fact that all heavenly laws prohibit sexual acts outside the institution of marriage, including homosexuality. They cast a system of knowledge based on utilitarian philosophy in defining the concept of morality overshadowed by the legislation of Western countries, criminalizing rules of codification and punishment rather than formulating them on the basis of moral virtue criminalizing homosexuality, and expressing a growing need. To protect sexual freedom by criminalizing any assault on it, as well as regulating a new type of sexual relationship called homosexuality. These legislations include:

French legislation

In France, a deviant act constituted a major crime, the penalty for which was usually the death penalty, during the period leading up to the French Revolution of 1789; Because the legislator was influenced by the ecclesiastical law that adhered to strict Christian beliefs and criminal deviation (20) however, after the revolution, the legislator did not stipulate in the Penal Code of 1791 the crime of homosexuality in application of the slogan. for the individual. Freedom, but more than that allowed the act of homosexuality between adults if it was consensual in private places, and the policy of sexual relations continued in the continuation of homosexuality in private places according to the provisions of the Penal Code of 1810, and it is indicated that France is the first country in Europe to legalize Homosexuality under the pretext of individual freedom, which contributed to the creation of the phenomenon of legal tolerance in sexual acts (21). The French legislator repealed Article (330/2) of the Penal Code in 1980 as part of a reform that redefined many sexual crimes. Same-sex relations were criminalized if they occurred consensually with a person under eighteen years of age, and normal sexual relations were if this legal age distinction between same-sex and heterosexual activity led to debates in the French Senate on the philosophy of criminalization on the basis of a different age of consent that contradicts With the principle of equality between the two types of normal sexual relations and same-sex relations, these discussions prompted the legislator to reconsider and issue an amendment to this law in 1982. The reasons for repeal stipulate that the law in its parts (sodomy and homosexuality) is no longer a homosexuality or mental illness in the eyes of law, and that all sexual relations must be equal in the eyes of the law. Specific eligibility for approval, and making fifteen years of age acceptable for approval. (22) The French legislator did not stop at the limits of not criminalizing the aberrant act and punishing its perpetrators. Instead, I went to organize it in the form of a partnership contract between two people of the same sex through Law No. (99/944) of 1999 and the Law amending the French Civil Code, and this amendment added eight paragraphs to

the text of Article (515). (23) and the title of the twelfth chapter titled Concession and Civil Solidarity Agreement, and the meaning of civil solidarity is a contract between two natural adults, of different sexes or of the same sex to organize their joint life (24) In sum, the French legislation regulates consensual homosexuality in the manner of the partnership contract between the same sex, and stipulates the availability of certain conditions, some of which are objective, the most important of which is the non-registration of partnership between incest. Because this is a criminal offense and both partners must be adults, and some of them are official, including appearing in person before the competent court to register this contract, and the penal laws have been amended with the introduction of texts prohibiting discrimination between persons. Because of their sexual orientation and to impose appropriate punishment on the offender in order to protect homosexuality.

B- British Legislation

In the United Kingdom, homosexuality became permitted by law in 2013, when the UK Parliament allowed same-sex marriage in England and Wales in 2013 and came into force on (13 March 2014), and this law is called, the Act Marriage (same-sex couples), has extended the meaning of marriage, married couple and married to include heterosexual or homosexual persons (25) Therefore, the British legislator adopted the utilitarian philosophy that was originally based on the legalization of consensual acts affecting honour, so it organized homosexuality through same-sex marriage; Because homosexuality as a sexual act belongs to the circle of individual morality that the individual is entitled to perform because it is one of the sexual acts that society does not care about on the basis of the principle of individual freedom, so this principle allows everything that is sexual. Acts when done by mutual consent of the parties, but more than that, gave criminal protection to sexual freedom, and an exception to this, criminalizing homosexuality between incest or between non-blood relatives, such as adoption. As for the requirements of same-sex marriage, it is stipulated that the person who wishes to marry the same sex must not be heterosexual, homosexual, or related to a civil partnership, and be at least sixteen years old, except that he needs the approval of his parents or the court because he is a minor and has not yet reached the age of eleven The twenty (26) it is not permissible for him to conclude a homosexual marriage contract between blood relatives such as a mother, father, grandfather and grandmother, brother, sister, aunt and uncle, uncle and aunt, and marriage also may not be homosexual between blood relatives since the son is adopted One of the adoptive parents, the exception allows the person to marry The rest of the adoptive family members, including the adoptive brother or sister (27) and homosexuals have the option to conclude their marriage contract either through civil marriage of the same sex carried out by a specialized official in the registration of marriage in the state, and the marriage must be recorded in the marriage registry and signed by the two parties, two witnesses and the person who performed the civil ceremonies, or by the method of religious same-sex marriage that takes place in the church with the same procedures as before, but before that, the approval of the religious church must be obtained, and after That's why It started religious ceremonies (28) and if the same-sex marriage took place otherwise, it would be automatically annulled by law, because it is a void marriage. The British legislator equated the effects of same-sex marriage and heterosexual marriage, but it clearly stated the right of same-sex couples to adopt children (29) and same-sex couples were also allowed to receive in vitro fertilization (IVF) with medical assistance from order to have a child (30) Thus homosexuality became legal when homosexuality was fully legalized in Britain.

Sixth: A position on the evil of Iraq in criminalizing homosexuality

By extrapolating the provisions of the Penal Code, the Iraqi legislator has adopted the utilitarian trend as the father of the year, and did not criminalize homosexuality if they are among the adults who are already properly satisfied, but there are specific cases built in the moral guidance texts that adopt the moral sense for example, Shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding ten years or imprisonment if sodomy was carried out by an incest with her consent and she had completed eighteen years. At the age of. (31) As well as what was stated in Military Penal Code No. 14 of 2007, which punishes with imprisonment for a period of no less than three years, if sodomy with the military is committed by mutual consent (32) It is noted from the above the contradiction of the circle of criminalization and punishment between heavenly laws and man-made legislation, with regard to the act of homosexuality in its two dimensions (sodomy and lesbianism), so the heavenly laws went to criminalize homosexuality. Himself in order to effectively protect society from immorality. While I went to some to limit the scope of criminalization and punishment for the circumstances of its occurrence, and the perpetration of homosexuality between a male and a female, and homosexuality with a male or female under the legal age if it is already fulfilled, and the result, in the act of homosexuality is not a crime if it occurs in more than two cases as for the other two cases, it viewed homosexuality from an individual perspective, which led to its absolute legalization of homosexuality if it was done with the consent of two adult parties, in keeping with the principle of individual liberty and other principles that branch of it, including sexual freedom. Permissibility and the exception is criminalization.

Sixth: Conclusion

1 -Results

- A. The term sodomy refers to a sexual relationship between two people of the same sex without deviating from whether the sexual relationship is between two men or between two women, far from the usual method and the correct framework for intercourse.
- B. The divine laws unanimously forbid homosexuality for its violation of common sense, the perversion of monsters, the killing of chivalry and chivalry, the robbery of modesty and filth, the corruption of manhood, and a crime against femininity. And corruption. The decadence of feelings that lowers the owner to a lower rank above which animals rise, as well as other religions that do not allow homosexuality, such as Hinduism, Buddhism, Sikhism and others.
- C. Most Arab penal legislation criminalizes homosexuality as a regression in the moral and ethical aspect of the individual and society, and some legislation influenced from abroad take a promising ethical basis to criminalize homosexuality.
- D. The position of positive criminal legislation in dealing with the issue of various homosexualities, as some of them adopted the moral concept of sexual acts, and criminalized all or some deviant sexual practices, while others adopted the principle of sexual freedom as a human right. The individual protects his body from every sexual practice that occurs to him against his will, which is considered legal homosexuality. That is, the permissibility of homosexuality and the release of freedom in it, as it is devoid of any criminal text criminalizing consensual homosexual acts in their two dimensions (sodomy and lesbianism)

2-Recommendations

- A. We demand the Iraqi legislator to amend Articles (393-397) of the Penal Code to ensure the criminalization of deviant sexual practices with their perverted festivals and lesbians in line with their moral concept about the prohibition of homosexuality. Threatening the entity of the family and society.
- B. Inviting state institutions to hold conferences, symposia and studies to highlight the harmful effects of this path C in terms of health and morality.
- C. Strict state control over websites by the governors and directing the media to carry out awareness-raising measures about this by focusing on sound and sound family education to limit the spread of this dangerous phenomenon.

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- Articles 47-50 of the British Child and Adoption Act 2002.
- Section 42 of the British Human Fertilization and Embryology Act 2008.
- See the text of Article 385 of the amended Iraqi Penal Code No. 111 of 1969.
- See the text of Article (76/First) of the Military Penal Code in force.

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